

DETERMINANTS OF REVISIT INTENTION ON HALAL TOURISM IN INDONESIA

PRIMA RINI METRI OKTAVIANTI

Faculty of Economics and Business, Lampung University Lampung Province, Indonesia.
Email: prima.oktavianti@gmail.com

MAHRINASARI MS

Faculty of Economics and Business, Lampung University Lampung Province, Indonesia.
Email: mahrina.sari@feb.unila.ac.id

ERNIE HENDRAWATY

Faculty of Economics and Business, Lampung University Lampung Province, Indonesia.
Email: ernie.hendrawaty@feb.unila.ac.id

Abstract

Purpose: This research aims to analyse the attractiveness of halal tourist destinations and their influence on the intention to revisit. This research also examines the mediating role of value creation on the intention to revisit. **Methodology/approach:** The research method, with a survey, was conducted on 390 respondents who had visited halal tourist destinations in Indonesia. The research data were analysed using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) with the LISREL 8.8 program to test the influence between variables. **Results/findings:** The research findings indicate that the attraction variable influences the intention to revisit. The value creation mediates the attraction towards the intention to revisit. The results of this research have implications for Indonesian halal tourist destinations. They encourage tourists to revisit Indonesian halal tourist destinations, thereby increasing the number of visitors to Indonesian halal tourist destinations beyond other countries that also offer halal tourist destinations. **Limitations:** The study only assessed domestic tourists' perceptions. It was suggested for further research to test foreign tourist respondents' perceptions. Other variables, such as a moderating variable of Destination Authenticity on Co-Value Creation need to be developed to have a wider test result on Halal tourism in Indonesia **Contribution:** This research's theoretical contribution is strengthening the model of the attractiveness of halal tourism destinations in Indonesia to the intention to revisit, mediated by value creation, by integrating the Co-Value Creation Theory, Service-Dominant Logic (SDL) Theory.

Keywords: Indonesia Halal Attractiveness of Tourism Destinations, Value Co-Creation Theory, Revisit Intention.

1. INTRODUCTION

With a Muslim percentage reaching 87% of the total population of 279 million people, Indonesia has gained international recognition by ranking first as the best halal destination (Global Muslim Travel Index (GMTI) in 2019, 2023, and 2024 (Crescent Rating, 2023). However, despite its enormous potential, Indonesia still faces serious challenges, including increasingly fierce competition from countries like Malaysia, which have already developed comprehensive halal tourism standards and policies. According to the study by Samori et al. (2016), Malaysia has successfully implemented a strong halal branding strategy, which has become a key factor in its competitive advantage. Data shows that Indonesia only managed to attract 11.26 million tourists (BPS, 2024; My Tourism Data, 2024), far below Malaysia, which managed to attract twice as many tourists

during the same period. Meanwhile, the Muslim population in Malaysia (ranked 21st in the world for the number of Muslims) amounts to 22,820,082 people (63.5%) (Global Muslim Population, 2024) out of a total population of 34,523,574 people. Individual tourism companies and destinations can be more competitive by creating value. However, for destinations, this process is more complicated because collaborative actions from various companies more often produce the tourist experience. Therefore, co-creation at the destination level can be achieved through the network of actors within it (Lindgreen et al., 2009). Interaction between actors is crucial to forming mutually beneficial value (Payne et al., 2008). To understand the revisit intention of Muslim tourists, the research considers the concepts of value co-creation and authenticity.

Previous studies have shown contradictory results regarding the influence of destination image on the intention to revisit (Bagozzi, 1992; Balaguer & Jordá, 2010; Khan et al., 2023). Therefore, further analysis is needed for a more consistent and comprehensive understanding. Moreover, in-depth exploration of the relationship between halal tourism experiences and tourists' revisit intentions is still limited, especially in developing countries with diverse cultural characteristics (Creswell, 2014; Rahman & Zailani, 2022). On the other hand, there is a lack of exploration regarding the relationship between halal tourism experiences and tourists' revisit intentions, as well as the inconsistency between the concept of co-creation in theory and practice (Battour & Ismail, 2016; Mansouri et al., 2021). Moreover, previous research has been dominated by quantitative methods, while qualitative approaches or mixed methods are still limited. Therefore, a more holistic research approach is greatly needed.

A context-based approach is essential to understand tourists' more complex and diverse needs (Dang & Weiss, 2010; Shafie & Othman, 2022; Nasrullah et al., 2023). The lack of application of specific theories in explaining halal tourist behavior further emphasizes the need to develop a conceptual model more relevant to industry needs (Pizam & Tasci, 2019). The attractiveness of destinations plays an important role in shaping the co-creation experience for tourists, affecting their behavior and level of satisfaction.

This relationship is particularly evident in the context of tourism, where the attractiveness of a destination can enhance visitor engagement and collaborative experiences. Based on empirical studies, it can be determined that the attractiveness of the destination influences the intention to revisit (Wang et al., 2022; Chien, 2016; Nastabiq & Soesanto, 2021). Other findings also prove that the destination's attractiveness influences the intention to revisit (Pratminingsih et al., 2022, and MoMohamad et al., 2019). The attractiveness of a destination is considered important because it can provide consumers with the primary motivation to visit the destination (Chien, 2016). The findings also reinforce that the tourist attractions of a destination are often considered one of the main determinants of its tourist appeal (Choo, Ahn, and Patrick, 2016).

The value co-creation theory has been widely recognized since it first appeared in the marketing literature (Prahalad & Ramachandran, 2004; Vargo & Lusch, 2004). Marketing relies on value creation (Kotler & Keller, 2012), and competitive strategies depend on value creation. Research on the relationships between companies and various

stakeholders (internal and external) involved in specific market contexts has contributed to the literature on value creation (Vargo and Lusch 2004, 2008a; Park & Vargo, 2012).

However, not much empirical research seeks to understand the components that facilitate or hinder collaboration between stakeholders at tourist destinations, which are antecedents of value co-creation. Value co-creation is often difficult to observe empirically (Storbacka, Brodie, Böhmman, and Hoffman, 2007). Because it arises from the coordinated actions of two or more actors operating within a specific phenomenological and relational context, coordination depends on the interaction between parties, and the behavior of each actor in a specific service ecosystem can be observed, evaluated, and controlled (Grönroos & Voima, 2013).

A commitment to cooperation is built to achieve beneficial outcomes for all parties involved (Golinelli, Barile, Sphorer, and Bassano 2015; Grönroos, 2011; Voima, Heinonen, and Strandvik 2010). However, some studies indicate that, especially in business-to-business service networks, coordination among actors and fundamental interactions do not always lead to the value co-creation process (Chowdhury, Gruber, and Zolkiewski, 2016). Based on the study, co-creating tourism experiences is a good starting point for adapting to consumers and setting service expectations accordingly (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004).

Many customer demands are facilitated by technology (Neuhofer et al., 2013). Existing research offers insights into customer desires and demands to create their experiences with the company (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004). In this study, the highlighted market need is halal tourism.

1.1 Formulation of the Problem

The following problem statement is suggested in light of the above study contributions and research gap:

- a. Is the revisit intention influenced by the allure of Indonesia's halal attractiveness destinations?
- b. Is the relationship between halal attractiveness destinations and the revisit intention mediated by value co-creation?

The study is anticipated to offer strategic insights for the competitive and sustainable growth of halal travel destinations worldwide by responding to these queries.

1.2 The Objectives

Beginning with the above-mentioned research problems and problem formulation, the following are the goals of this study:

- a. Conducting an empirical investigation into how the allure of Indonesia's halal attractiveness destinations affects travellers' revisit intention.
- b. Using the value creation mediating variable, empirically examine how Indonesian halal attractiveness destinations affect travellers' revisit intentions

1.3 Contribution of Research

The following are the contributions derived from the study's findings:

- a. This study makes significant methodological and theoretical especially in marketing management, which specializes in Halal Tourism Marketing.
- b. This study makes empirical contributions for the Ministry and Tourism Offices of West Sumatra Province, DKI Jakarta, Riau, Banda Aceh, Lombok, Bali, DI Jogjakarta, Jawa Barat, Jawa Tengah, Jawa Timur and Sulawesi Selatan as an effort to create halal tourism policies so that industry players can prepare tour packages according to the needs and desires of Muslim tourists
- c. It is hoped that industry players can develop and clarify halal tourism, which would motivate them to invest in Indonesia, especially in West Sumatra Province, DKI Jakarta, Riau, Banda Aceh, Lombok NTB, Bali, DI Jogjakarta, Jawa Barat, Jawa Tengah, Jawa Timur and Sulawesi Selatan

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS

2.1 Definition of Halal

The study of the definition of halal a guarantee in the consumption of halal without doubt about the quality, loyalty, and compliance with Sharia, which is a concept to influence both Muslim and non-Muslim consumers in making the right decisions when purchasing any product or service (Yusniza Kamarulzaman, Azian bin Madun, 2017; Majid et al.,2015). Muslim travellers are one of the fastest-growing segments of tourism and are the primary target of halal tourism (Comtec, 2016; Stephenson, 2014).

In recent years, various countries have tried to seize the opportunity to serve this segment. Muslim travellers have several specific needs that differ from those of other travellers. This is related to the performance of daily prayers (five times a day), the availability of halal food and drinks (permissible for consumption), the prohibition of alcohol and gambling, the separation of men and women in public places, and the rules for Muslim women when travelling. They must travel with a mahram (husband or a man who, if married, would be considered haram/prohibited in Islamic law). Additionally, Muslim women are not allowed to show their hair and bodies according to Islamic teachings (Battour et al., 2011; Shakona et al., 2015).

2.2 Halal Tourism

Sharia is the principle of Islamic law regulated by fatwas and approved by the Indonesian Ulama Council. The term shariah began to be used in Indonesia's banking industry. The term used in the banking industry expanded to other sectors: sharia insurance, sharia pawnshops, sharia hotels, and sharia tourism. The definition of sharia tourism is activities supported by various facilities and services provided by the community, entrepreneurs, the government, and local governments that comply with sharia regulations. Currently, sharia tourism is utilised by many people due to the universal characteristics of its products and services. Tourist products and services, tourist attractions, and tourist

destinations in sharia tourism are the same as tourist products, services, attractions, and destinations in general tourism. The difference is that the products provided do not contradict the values and ethics of Sharia. This is what makes Sharia tourism not limited to just religious tourism. The concept of sharia tourism is broader than religious tourism, as it is based on Islamic Sharia values. According to the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), consumers of sharia tourism are not only Muslims but also non-Muslims who want to enjoy local wisdom (bincangsyariah.com). Halal tourism is a form of culture-based tourism that places the values and norms of Islamic Sharia as its fundamental guidelines. Halal tourism has an even wider variety.

It is not only limited to religious sites for tourism but also extends to general locations while adhering to Muslim rules and providing services and facilities for Muslim tourists to worship during their visit to tourist destinations (Nugraha, Marta, 2018). The overall Muslim population is categorized as very large and continues to grow. It was previously estimated to be 1.8 billion in 2005 (24.1% of the world's population), a proportion predicted to increase to 31.1% with 3 billion people by 2060. Salman Yousaf, Fan Xiucheng (2017) Indonesia is the country with the largest Muslim-majority population in the world, totalling 207,176,162 (BPS, 2010). This means that with a majority Muslim population, Indonesia should be able to become a prosperous country in developing tourism with the concept of halal tourism. The meaning of halal can literally be expressed with the root words Halla, Yahillu, Hillhillan, and Wahalan, which indicate everything halal and not prohibited in Islam (Al-Qaradawi, 2013), based on their understanding, similar to what was expressed by Farki (1966) and Siddiqui, and Haider (2015).

The halal aspect is permitted and applicable to every field of human life because Islam provides comprehensive guidelines on human consumption, worship, and social, environmental, economic, and political behavior (Hussain & El-Alami, 2007). The research was conducted by Ririn Tri Ratnasari (2020). Some countries use the term tourism, such as Islamic tourism, halal travel, and Muslim-friendly destinations. Japan and other non-Muslim countries, such as South Korea, Thailand, and the United Kingdom, use the terms halal tourism or muslim-friendly destinations for the use of the term Sharia tourism. Some non-Muslim countries that organize halal tourism include Australia, France, Germany, Hong Kong, Japan, Singapore, South Africa, Thailand, the UK, and Taiwan (Han et al., 2019). At the global level, the standardisation released by the World Halal Tourism Rating Agency, the Global Muslim Travel Index (GMTI) (2019), for halal tourism focuses on four main aspects:

- a. Ensuring easy access to destinations, transportation, and halal facilities.
- b. Communication: Providing clear and easily understandable information about halal facilities and services.
- c. Environment: Ensuring a clean, safe, and comfortable environment, reflecting Islamic values.
- d. Services: Offering quality and halal services, including halal food, appropriate accommodations, and worship facilities.

For Indonesia, the standardisation of halal tourism is regulated through the DSN-MUI Fatwa No. 108/DSN-MUI/X/2016, namely:

- a. Availability of Halal Food and Beverages: Ensure that all food and beverages served comply with halal principles. Worship Facilities: Provide adequate worship places like prayer rooms or mosques.
- b. Avoidance of Non-Halal Activities: Avoiding activities that contradict Islamic values, such as alcohol consumption or inappropriate activities.
- c. Alignment with Islamic Values: Ensuring that all aspects of halal tourism are aligned with Islamic principles.
- d. Separated Recreation Areas: Providing separated recreation areas for women and men.
- e. Appropriate Accommodations: Providing accommodations that comply with Islamic rules, such as sharia hotels.

2.3 Attractiveness of a Destination

Liu Ru et al. (2017) state that the attractiveness of a destination refers to the extent to which the destination motivates tourists to spend time enjoying pleasant experiences. Tourist attractions are divided into two categories: tourist sites and tourist attractions. Tourist attractions are static and tangible (Zaenuri, 2012) and do not require any prior preparation to enjoy them (Yoeti, 1985). Meanwhile, tourist attractions are tourist attractions that can be seen through performances and require preparation and even sacrifices to enjoy them (Zaenuri, 2012).

Yoeti (2008) maintains, in general, four groups of tourist attractions attract visitors to travel destinations, namely: 1) Natural Attractions, which include sea views, beaches, lakes, waterfalls, botanical gardens, Agrotouristic Mountains, flora, and fauna. 2) Build Attraction, which includes buildings with attractive architecture, such as traditional houses and those that are both ancient and modern. 3) Cultural attractions include historical relics, folk tales, traditional arts, museums, religious ceremonies, art festivals, and etc. 4) Social attractions, which include the community's way of life, various languages, wedding ceremonies, tooth filing, circumcision and other social activities.

Yoeti (2008) then maintains tourist attractions must have three elements: 1) something to see, such as the beauty/uniqueness of nature, historical buildings, or local arts/culture; 2) something to do, such as rowing a boat, trying traditional food, dancing with local dancers, and so on; and 3) Something to buy to meet tourists' shopping needs. Zaenuri (2012) states that tourist attractions are unique and become the choice of tourists, thus providing satisfaction with what tourist's desire. Many studies have confirmed that the attractiveness of a destination is an important factor influencing tourists' decisions.

Yoeti (1997) said that the success of a tourist destination and the achievement of a tourist area greatly depend on the 33A's'ss: 1) Attraction, 2) Accessibility, and 3) Facilities or amenities.

2.4 Co-Creation Value

Co-creation is about the joint creation of value by the company and customers, said Prahalad and Ramaswamy (2004) in Taghiadeh et al. (2021). According to Kohler et al. (2011), co-creation is a process that many companies from various sectors have adopted. However, there are services with a lower level of co-creation due to the specific characteristics of their operational areas. In the tourism sector, the level of co-creation is higher due to the need for involvement (Balaguer et al., 2010). The varying levels of co-creation, ranging from low to high, are influenced by several factors, such as awareness of the value of co-creation, willingness to collaborate, and organisational structure. Lower levels of co-creation can occur due to a lack of understanding or unwillingness to involve customers in the innovation process, while higher levels of co-creation happen because of awareness of the benefits of collaboration and structures that support customer involvement. The impact of co-creation on value perception can vary, depending on whether the participants are residents or tourists. This implies that the influence of co-creation activities is context-specific (Byon et al., 2022).

In tourism, the co-creation process begins with customers and the service elements they will enjoy, including online environments (during the booking process) and physical elements such as layout, equipment, and culture. Additionally, interpersonal dimensions play a fundamental role in co-creation (Pizam & Tasci, 2019). During and after the consumption of services, customers become co-creators, and the perceived service value increases, contributing to customer retention and enhancing the likelihood of return (Meng et al., 2020). Furthermore, Mustak et al. (2013) state that customer participation leads to the conception of offerings more aligned with customer expectations and needs, resulting in superior value creation. In other words, customer participation is expected to positively influence a particular service's perceived value and experience (Taheri et al., 2017).

Creation is a process based on service-dominant logic (SDL), which emphasizes that a consumer is not merely viewed as a strategic object but a potential resource that should be involved in a value-adding process (Vargo & Lusch, 2004). Consumers can collaborate with companies to create innovations for products and services that will ultimately impact the formation of memorable experiences (Chathoth et al., 2016). Ideally, the idea of value creation centered on the customer and not the company providing value to the customer commands the ten basic premises of what is now known as service-dominant logic (Vargo & Lusch, 2008). The idea that forms the basis of these ten fundamental premises can be traced back to influential papers (Vargo & Lusch, 2004; Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004) that garnered significant academic attention in the concept of value co-creation by businesses with their customers (Galvagno & Dali, 2014).

When applying the value co-creation concept in halal tourism services, there is often a discrepancy between theory and practice (Battour & Ismail, 2016). This indicates the need for a more practical and evidence-based approach to bridge the gap between academics and practitioners in the halal tourism industry. Moreover, the methodological approaches used in previous research are still dominated by quantitative methods with survey techniques. In contrast, qualitative approaches or mixed methods are still limited in

exploring the psychological and social factors influencing tourist behaviour (Chen-Ling & Lie, 2006). Zhang et al. (2019) found that value co-creation can influence satisfaction. Next, Woo et al. (2015) showed that value co-creation positively and significantly affects tourist satisfaction. Lin et al. (2017) stated that it has a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction because it can be influenced by value co-creation and community participation in creating value with tourists who visit the place or tourist destination.

2.5 Revisit Intention

According to Baker and Crompton, J.I. (2000), the intention to revisit is the willingness of customers to repeat the services they have previously consumed. A study conducted by Wang (2004) mentioned that the cost of attracting repeat visitors is lower compared to attracting new customers. Additionally, compared to first-time visitors, repeat visitors tend to spend more money (Lehto, O'Leary, and Morrison, 2004) and stay longer (Wang, 2004). So, to maintain competitiveness, designing unforgettable experiences to attract tourists to revisit their destinations in the following years becomes a primary mission and an important measure for company managers. From the perspective of the consumption process, visitor behavior is divided into three stages: pre-visit, during the visit, and post-visit (William Buswell, 2003).03). A similar point was made by Chen and Tsai (2007:39), who stated that tourist behavior includes the choice of visit, subsequent evaluation, and future intention of visitor behavior. The subsequent evaluation is the travel experience or the overall value and satisfaction received by the visitors. In contrast, future behavioural intentions refer to the visitors' judgment about the appropriateness of returning to the same destination and their willingness to recommend it to others. The concept of repurchase intention originates from behavioural intention.

Baker and Crompton in Chung-Hslen Lin (2012) explain that revisit intention is the likelihood of tourists repeating activities or revisiting a destination. Songshan (Sam) Huang and Cathy (2009) in their journal "Effects of Travel Motivation, Past Experience, Perceived Constraint, and Attitude on Revisit Intention," stated that there are four impacts that can lead to revisit intention, namely: 1) Travel Motivation Investigating the impact of various motivational factors on tourists' attitudes during a repeat visit to a destination and their intention to revisit. 2) Past Experience To test the influence of past travel experiences on tourists' attitudes during a repeat visit to a destination and their intention to revisit. 3) Perceived Constraint: To investigate the influence of constraints perceived on tourists' intention to revisit. 4) Attitude to measure the extent to which tourists' attitudes mediate the impact of certain factors on the intention to revisit.

The dimensions used in this study are the dimensions proposed by Baker and Crompton in Chung-Hslen Lin (2012), which also include two dimensions: Intention to Recommend (desire to recommend to others) and Intention to Revisit (desire to return). Many studies on consumers' intention to make repeat purchases or revisit a destination have focused on the factors determining this intention. The most frequently suggested determining factors are previous satisfying experiences, perceived quality, previous visits to the destination, and tourist motivation (Alegre & Cladera, 2009). The intention to revisit is a significant research topic in tourism destinations and has been mentioned as important in

behavioural intentions (Allameh et al., 2015; Jani & Han, 2011). Tourist behaviour includes the choice of destinations to visit, further evaluations, and future behavioural intentions (Allameh et al., 2015; Chen & Tsai, 2007).

The subsequent evaluation is about the value perceived by tourists and their satisfaction, while future behavioural intentions refer to the willingness to revisit the same destination and recommend it to others (Hume et al., 2007; Ryu et al., 2010; Som et al., 2012). The intention to revisit and share information through word-of-mouth is an important source of profitability (Marinkovic et al., 2014).

3. FRAMEWORK OF THOUGHT AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

3.1 The Halal Attractive Destinations on the Intention to Revisit

If the tourist attraction is not enjoyed and felt by tourists, it will impact their satisfaction, and interest in visiting will decrease (Ester et al., 2020). According to Zaenuri (2012), tourist attractions are unique and become the choice of tourists, thus providing satisfaction with what tourist's desire. Tourist attractions are one of the elements that must be possessed by a tourist attraction in order to be considered worthy of a visit.

Sugianto & Marpaung (2020) state that tourist attractions are related formations, activities, and facilities that attract tourists' interest to come and visit a particular area or place. Tourist attractions are interesting to see and enjoy, so they can influence tourists to revisit the same tourist site (Saputro et al., 2020).

H1: The Attraction of the Destination Influences the Intention to Revisit

3.2 The Attraction of Destinations on the Intention to Revisit through Value Co-Creation

Creating a foundation for value co-creation by allowing customers to share their knowledge and experiences while also providing positive and negative feedback (Bilgin, 2018; Portal et al., 2019). Co-creation is a potent mediator in encouraging revisit intentions in the tourism sector. By actively involving customers in creating their experiences, businesses can enhance satisfaction, build emotional connections, and drive loyalty.

Consumers expect to engage in behaviors that invest resources to create value with the platform (Cheung & To, 2021; Kohler et al., 2011; Sheng et al., 2022). The breadth and depth of interactions between users and the community, or among users within the community, enhance the sense of belonging and community identification, leading to higher engagement and loyalty (Huangfu et al., 2022; Shen et al., 2014).

This also allows companies to educate other consumers while helping them improve their services. With the creation of experiences, it is hoped that tourist destinations will be able to influence the intention to revisit.

H2: The Attraction of the Destination Influences the Intention to Revisit through Value Co-Creation

3.3 Conceptual Framework

The research model is as follows:

Figure 1: Framework for the Attractiveness of Destination to revisit Intention with Mediating Co-Value creation

4. RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design Based on the objectives and hypotheses of the research, this study is quantitative research to test certain theories by examining the relationships between variables using research instruments that produce data in the form of numbers analyzed using statistics (Creswell, 2014). This research method is a field study or survey, which is conducted in a natural environment where events occur normally (Sekaran and Bougie, 2017). 3.2.

Population and Sample This research use primary data, which is data obtained firsthand for subsequent analysis to find solutions or problems being studied (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). The population sampled in this study consists of tourists who have visited one or more of the five premier Muslim-friendly tourist destinations in Indonesia, namely Lombok, Aceh, Riau and the Riau Islands, the Special Capital Region of Jakarta, and West Sumatra, and intend to visit again.

The research subjects use the non-Probability sampling technique, which is a sampling method that does not give equal opportunities to all members of the population, and its determination is not random. Sampling from the population may occur by chance or due to the researcher's determining factors.

The research uses the Purposive Sampling technique, which is a sampling method aimed at fulfilling the researcher's interests by selecting respondents who are most likely to provide accurate and useful information (Kelly, 2010: 317) and is a way to identify and select cases that will effectively use limited research resources (Palinkas et al., 2015). The purposive sampling strategy is not conducted randomly and is a strategy to ensure that specific types of cases from the potential cases that may be included are part of the final sample in the research study (Campbell et al., 2020).

The number of respondents taken was 390. In this study, the sample size is also a consideration. According to Solimun (2002:78), several guidelines for determining the sample size for SEM are provided as follows: 1. If parameter estimation uses the maximum likelihood estimation method, the recommended sample size is between 100 to 200, with a minimum sample size of 50. 2. Equal to 5 to 10 times the number of manifest variables (indicators) of all latent variables.

This study refers to the second rule, so the researcher sets the sample size to 10 times the number of research indicators. This is done so that the sample size is representative of the existing population, thus the sample size is taken as $n = 10 \times$ the number of indicators, which is: $n = 10 \times 39 = 390$ respondents. Thus, the sample size in this study is 390 respondents. The unit of analysis in this study is individuals selected based on tourists who have visited one of the premier halal tourist destinations in Indonesia and intend to visit again.

The premier tourist destinations are: Lombok, Banda Aceh, Riau and the Riau Islands, DKI Jakarta, West Sumatra, Bali, Special Region of Yogyakarta, West Java, Central Java, East Java, South Sulawesi, West Bali Halal tourism in Bali offers a vacation experience that aligns with Islamic values while also appreciating the diversity of Balinese culture and tradition (Bedugul Botanical Garden, Penglipuran Tourism Village, and Sanur Beach), West Java Central Java, East Java, South Sulawesi.

The data collection method in this study uses the Survey method with additional interviews to reduce bias through several methods, which include the following: Interviews, Questionnaire (distributing the questionnaire via Google Forms to tourists at the tourist destination. or tourists who have visited Muslim-friendly tourist destinations). The collected data is then scored from 1 to 5 based on the Likert Scale/Rating Scale to indicate the level of implementation. The variable data in this study are on an ordinal scale (Sekaran and Bougie, 2017). Others additional secondary data gained from the web, social media, etc.

Table 1: Definitions Operational dan Measurement Variable Destination Attraction Travel

Operational Variable Definition	Operational Sub-Variable Definition	Research Instruments Source (Li Teng et al. 2023)	Research Instruments	Measurement Scale (Likert)
Attractiveness of Destination How far is the destination? What motivates tourists to spend time.? What about the security?	Facility service attractiveness facilities)	1: This destination has reasonable accommodations.	1.Destination This halal tourism have good accommodation.	1 to 5
		2: This destination has easy access to transportation nearby.	2: Destination This halal tourism has easy access transportation / roads.	

		3: This destination provides me with a lot of leisure fun	3: Destination This halal tourism gives me much pleasure.	
	Sightseeing experience attractive (Experience) Entertainment	1: This destination has beautiful scenery	1: Destination This halal tourism has beautiful scenery.	
		2: This destination has profound cultural heritage.	2: Destination This halal tourism has a deep heritage culture.	

Operational Variable Definition	Operational Sub-Variable Definition	Research Instrument Source (Taghiadeh et al. 2021)	Research Instrument	Measurement Scale (Likert)
<i>Co-creation</i> is about creating value together by the company and the customer.	Dialogue	1. Use diversified communication channels to have dialogue sessions with customers	Saya uses various communication media channels to have a dialogue with manager destination of this halal tourism.	1 to 5
		2. Conduct dialogue session with customer frequently	I have a dialogue with manager destination of this halal tourism routine	
		3. Involve internal parties during the dialogue session with customers	I Involve other internal parties in dialog with manager destination on this halal tourism	
		4. Recognize the customer's experience regarding the service	I recognise experience tourism related to service destination tourism. in this is halal.	
	Access	1. Offer opportunity to the customers to share in the design process of service	I get opportunity for share Opinion in the design process service of this halal tourism destination.	
		2. Offer opportunity to the customers to share in the development process of service	I get the opportunity to share my Opinion in the development process service destination in this halal tourism	
		3. Offer opportunity to the customers to share in the price setting process of services	I got opportunity share Opinion inside determine the process Determination price service destination of this halal tourism.	
	Risk	1. Inform potential risks of the service offered of the customers	I inform potential risk services offered to destination manager in this halal tourism	

		2. Inform customers about the limitation of the firm's knowledge and capability	I inform to manager about Halal Tourism Destination and the limitations of company knowledge dan ability.	
		3. Shoulder all the risk related responsibilities upon themselves	I am responsible against all the existing risk at destination with this halal tourism	
	Transparen cy	1. Make clear to the customers about the service-related information	I give clear information to manager destination about this halal tourism about service destination for this halal tourism.	
		2. Disclose pricing related information to other customers	I am revealing information price to manager destination for this halal tourism	
		3. Get benefit from the information on symmetry between the customers and the firm	I get benefit and thank you for symmetrical information between tourist dan manager destination in this halal tourism.	
		4. Build trust among the customers through transparent information	I build trust to manager between the tourist destination halal tourism via transparent information	

Operational Variable Definition	Operationa l Sub- Variable Definition	Research Instrument Source (<i>Monteiro et al., 2023</i>)	Research Instruments	Measureme nt Scale (Likert)
Revisit Intention Intention for visit return is readiness of the customer for repeat The service that has been consumed previously		I am planning to revisit this restaurant shortly	I plan to visit return destination in this halal tourism inside time close	1 to 5
		2: I will make an effort to revisit this restaurant in the near future	I will be trying for visit return destination This halal tourism inside time close	
		3: I am willing to revisit this restaurant in the near future	I am ready for visit return destination for this halal tourism inside time close	

5. RESULTS

5.1 Hypothesis Testing

Respondent Profile: The profile of the respondent in the research is reviewed from the aspect of the respondent's origin, region, gender, age, income per month, education and occupation that can be seen in Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 2: Respondent Areas

No	Province	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Total Respondents
1	West Java	115	29.5%
2	Lampung	49	12.6%
3	South Sulawesi	41	10.5%
4	Maluku	34	8.7%
5	Jakarta	25	6.4%
6	East Java	14	3.6%
7	Banten	10	2.6%
8	Southeast Sulawesi	10	2.6%
9	Central Java	8	2.1%
10	DI Yogyakarta	7	1.8%
11	South Sumatra	7	1.8%
12	West Sumatra	7	1.8%
13	In Aceh	6	1.5%
14	Bengkulu	5	1.3%
15	Riau Islands	4	1%
16	Riau	4	1%
17	North Sumatra	4	1%
18	Bali	4	1%
19	East Nusa Tenggara	3	0.8%
20	East Kalimantan	3	0.8%
21	West Nusa Tenggara	3	0.8%
22	West Kalimantan	3	0.8%
23	South Papua	3	0.8%
24	Jambi	3	0.8%
25	Central Sulawesi	2	0.5%
26	Bangka Belitung	2	0.5%
27	North Kalimantan	2	0.5%
28	South Kalimantan	2	0.5%
29	Central Kalimantan	1	0.3%
30	North Sulawesi	1	0.3%
31	Gorontalo	1	0.3%
32	West Sulawesi	1	0.3%
33	Central Papua	1	0.3%
34	Papua	1	0.3%
35	North Maluku	1	0.3%
36	West Papua	1	0.3%
37	West Papua	1	0.3%
38	Papua Mountains	1	0.3%
	Total	390	100%

Source: Data Processed (2025)

Table 3 shows the 10 main regional respondents from Java Island, 29.5% of which are followed by DKI Jakarta, East Java, Banten, Central Java and Daerah Istimewa Jogjakarta. The lowest are from the eastern regions such as Central Kalimantan Province, West Sulawesi, to Papua, to North Maluku. This statement is based on a survey by the

Directorate of Statistics of Finance, Information Technology, and Tourism (2023), that a province with a large population also tends to have a high number of tourists in the archipelago.

Table 4: Respondents' Characteristic

Respondent Characteristics		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male - male	208	53.3%
	Female	182	46.7%
Age	17-27	29	7.4%
	28-38	153	39.2%
	39-49	130	33.3%
	≥ 50	78	20.0%
Income	3.10 million - 4.10 million	88	22.6%
	> 4.10 million - 6.10 million	81	20.8%
	> 6.10 million	221	56.7%
Education	SMP	2	0.6%
	SMA	46	11.8%
	D1/D2/D3	25	6.4%
	D4/S1	161	41.3%
	S2	129	33.1%
	S3	27	6.9%
Jobs	Student	14	3.6%
	Housewife	16	4.1%
	Labor	9	2.3%
	PNS	84	21.5%
	Private Officer	102	26.2%
	Entrepreneurship	15	3.9%
	Trader	10	2.6%
	other	140	35.9%
Total		390	

Source: Data Processed (2025)

Table 5: Validity and Reliability Test Result

Variable	SLF>0.5	Error	CR>0.7	AVE>0,5	Conclusion
Attraction					Reliabel
DT1	0.902	0.186			Valid
DT2	0.897	0.195			Valid
DT3	0.975	0.049	0.966	0.852	Valid
DT4	0.961	0.076			Valid
DT5	0.875	0.234			Valid
Creation Value					Reliabel
NP1	0.809	0.346			Valid
NP2	0.850	0.278			Valid
NP3	0.817	0.333			Valid
NP4	0.732	0.464			Valid
NP5	0.928	0.139			Valid
NP6	0.952	0.094			Valid

NP7	0.949	0.099	0.976	0,743	Valid
NP8	0.958	0.082			Valid
NP9	0.962	0.075			Valid
NP10	0.765	0.415			Valid
NP11	0.964	0.071	0,969	0.650	Valid
NP12	0.822	0.324			Valid
NP13	0.755	0.430			Valid
NP14	0.738	0.455			Valid
Intention to visit again					Reliabel
NB1	0.780	0.392			Valid
NB2	0.796	0.366	0.826	0.612	Valid
NB3	0.771	0.406			valid

Source: Processed Data, 2025

Table 6: Goodness of Fit Test Result

Overall Fit		Result Value	Standard Value	Conclusion
<i>Absolute Fit Measure</i>			Expected Small	Good
	RMSEA	0.078	≤0.10	Good
	GFI	0.80	≥0.80	Good
<i>Incremental Fit Measure</i>	IFI	0.914	≥0.90	Good
	NFI	0.90	≥0.90	Good
	CFI	0.913	≥0.90	Good
<i>Parsimonious Fit Measure</i>	PNFI	0.827	≤ 0.90	Good
	PGFI	0.680	≤ 0.90	Good

Source: Data Processed (2025)

5.2 Structural Model Results

Table 7: Hypothesis Direct Effect Test Result

Hypothesis	Path Analysis	Standardised Value	Standard Error	P-Value	Decision
2	Attraction → revisit intention	0.329	0.055	0	Supported

Source: Data Processed (2025)

5.3 Mediation Test

In this study, researchers also tested the mediation effect of the value creation between the attractiveness of halal tourism destinations on the intention to revisit. Baron and Kenny (1986) explained the testing procedure on the mediating construct in two steps. First, estimate the direct effect of the destination's attractiveness on the intention to revisit, which requires a significant value. Second, the indirect effect can be estimated simultaneously with the triangle model. Table 8 below explains that attractiveness influences the intention to revisit, so that the first requirement is met to proceed to the second stage.

Table 8: Direct effect, Attractiveness of Destination to Revisit Intention

Source: Data Processed (2025)

Next, testing the effect of media by using the variance accountant calculation for (VAF) value (Baron and Kenny, 1986) with formula

Figure 4: Illustration of Mediation

Note: a = regression coefficient antara variabel independen dan mediator

b = regression coefficient between mediator and dependent variable

c = regression coefficient between the independent and dependent variables.

Table 9: Mediation Test

Model	Path			Calculation			Conclusion
	A	b	c	ab	ab+c	ab/ab+c	
atractivness→ → value co creation → revisit intention	0.59	0.226	0.329	0.133	0,4	0.333	H3: Partial Mediation

Source: Data Processed (2025)

Based on the mediation results indicated by a positive value of 0.133. If we look deeper into the comparison of the numbers shown from the study results, the direct effect test between attractiveness and revisit intention results shows smaller results compared to the additional effect of Creation Value. This means that the attractiveness variable can directly influence revisit intention, and the attractiveness variable can indirectly influence the mediation role of creation value. However, when compared to the value of its influence, the attractiveness mediated by creation value has a higher value of influence on purchase intention than that which is not mediated by creation value. In the effect test, the variable of creation value partially mediates between attractiveness and revisit intention.

6. DISCUSSION

According to the above study findings, the Value Co-Creation Theory and the Service-Dominant Logic (SDL) Theory explain why halal travel locations in Indonesia are so

popular. Following SEM Lisrel 8.8 data processing, the results show an impact on value creation and intention to return.

The Co-Creation Value Theory

According to the Value Co-Creation Theory, value creation is the cornerstone of competitive strategy since it is the foundation of marketing itself (Kotler and Keller 2012). Most of this study has focused on how different actors participating in the production and consumption processes interact to decide and co-create value (Vargo and Lusch 2011). Since value production results from the coordinated behaviors of two or more actors operating within a particular relational and phenomenological context, it is frequently challenging to observe experimentally (Storbacka, Brodie, Böhmman, Maglio, and Nenonen 2016).

Coordination is based on the interaction between the parties, and each actor's behaviour within a particular service ecosystem is observable, assessable, and manageable (Grönroos & Voima, 2013). The assumption that beneficial results will be produced for all parties engaged is how commitment to collaboration is attained (Golinelli, Barile, Sphorer, and Bassano, 2015; Gronroos, 2011; Voima, Heinonen, and Strandvik, 2010). Numerous studies have examined applying value creation principles to tourism experiences.

Most of these studies have focused on the interactions between destinations and tourists and between businesses and tourists (Campos, Mendes, Oom do Valle, and Scott 2018; Prebensen, Vittersø, and Dahl 2013). The Value Co-Creation Theory, which guarantees that occasions like carnivals offer a venue for interactive co-creation experiences, demonstrates the significance of participation and co-creation satisfaction. Pappas, N. et al. (2024) corroborate this assertion. They have emphasized how companies and consumers work together to simultaneously, contextually, and cooperatively co-create the value of tourism experiences. Accordingly, the significance of cooperative marketing in the travel industry has long been acknowledged in the literature (Fyall, 2014).

As a result, it becomes critical to comprehend the dynamics of interaction between tourist actors at a location as well as the elements that either support or impede cooperation. This is consistent with the Service Dominant Logic (SDL) Theory, which holds that the service-dominant logic has set the essential requirements for co-creation. According to this theory, the customer should be at the center of the value creation concept rather than the business offering value to the customer (Vargo and Lusch, 2008).

The ten fundamental assumptions of what is now referred to as service-dominant logic (also known as SDL) are determined by the preferences of the customers. Service-dominant logic (SDL), the foundation of the co-creation process, highlights that a customer is not only seen as a strategic item but also as a potential resource that has to be included in a value-adding process (Vargo and Lusch, 2004).

The Effect of the Attractiveness of a Destination on Revisit Intention

The hypothesis test's findings demonstrate that attraction significantly and favourably influences the intention to return. The findings of this study corroborate those of Wang et

al. (2022), Nastabiq and Soesanto (2021), and Chien (2016). Based on empirical research, it can be concluded that the destination's appeal affects travellers' intentions to return. Other research also demonstrates that the destination's appeal affects travellers' intentions to return (Pratminingsih et al., 2022; Mohamad et al., 2019). The interviews also revealed that the most frequent travellers are millennials (those born between 1981 and 1996). They have decent occupations and are in excellent physical condition.

The Co-Creation Value Mediating Effect to Strengthen the Halal Attractiveness of Destination and the Revisit Intention

The hypothesis test results demonstrate that value creation mediates the relationship between the allure of a destination and the desire to return. The study's findings are consistent with earlier investigations. In the tourist industry, co-creation serves as a mediator that subtly affects the allure of the wish to return. According to the idea, these Businesses may increase customer happiness, foster emotional bonds, and eventually foster loyalty by actively including customers in creating their experiences. Customers anticipate that they will participate in actions that require resources in order to add value alongside the platform. Customers anticipate that they will participate in actions that require resources in order to add value alongside the platform.

7. CONCLUSION, IMPLICATIONS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

7.1 Conclusion

The research findings indicate that the attraction variable influences the intention to revisit. The value creation mediates the attraction towards the intention to revisit. The results of this research have implications for Indonesian halal tourist destinations. They encourage tourists to revisit Indonesian halal tourist destinations, thereby increasing the number of visitors to them beyond other countries that also offer halal tourist destinations.

This research's theoretical contribution is strengthening the model of the attractiveness of halal tourism destinations in Indonesia to the intention to revisit, mediated by value creation, by integrating the Co-Value Creation Theory and Service-Dominant Logic (SDL) Theory.

7.2 Implication

This study contributes to the theory of destination marketing. It advances the theoretical knowledge of how revisit intention is influenced by appeal as a destination attribute, particularly in relation to halal tourism. It highlights the function of value creation as a mediating variable, emphasising that visitors are impacted by the perceived value they receive during their trip rather than just the initial attraction. With respect to Value-Based Approaches in Halal Travel, this study's results demonstrate that value creation is essential to raising visitor satisfaction and loyalty, supporting the incorporation of value-based consumer behaviour models into frameworks for halal tourism. This implies that while examining revisit intentions, future theoretical models should consider experiential and value-driven factors. This study invites the setting of the Scene for Indonesian Halal

Travel as it grounds its insights in Indonesia, a significant player in the worldwide halal tourism business. This adds a geographic and cultural component to the body of previous work. This contextual nuance makes a more localized knowledge of visitor behavior in places with a majority of Muslims possible.

Managerially, this study has four managerial implications:

a. Improving Attractions at the Destination

Indonesian tourism management should improve the attractiveness of halal tourist locations by focusing on modern facilities, infrastructure, and marketing that appeal to halal-conscious tourists in addition to religious and cultural components.

b. Emphasising Strategies for Value Creation

The relationship between attraction and intention to return is mediated by value creation. Thus, destination managers need to make sure visitors have experiences that are relevant, tailored to them, and culturally relevant. This can include excellent halal food services, places for prayer, entertainment that is suitable for Muslims, and staff members who have received halal hospitality training.

c. Positioning for Promotion

The information provides a competitive advantage in **marketing Indonesian halal travel destinations as providing better overall value than rivals, in addition to being in line with Islamic principles. This can be utilized to create advertising efforts that establish Indonesia as the world's leading destination for Muslim tourists.

d. Development of Sustainable Tourism

Promoting return visits aids in the development of sustainable tourism. Instead of concentrating on one-time visits, managers can concentrate on long-term visitor engagement, which lowers marketing expenses, fosters brand loyalty, and keeps the flow of tourist's constant.

7.3 Further Research

The study only assessed domestic tourists' perceptions. Further research was suggested to test foreign tourist respondents' perceptions. Other variables, such as a moderating variable of Destination Authenticity on Co-Value Creation need to be developed to have a wider test result on Halal tourism in Indonesia.

Below are the suggested further studies:

a. Exploration of Moderating Variables.

Future studies could explore potential moderating variables such as cultural background, religious commitment, travel motivation, or prior experience. These may influence the strength of the relationship between attraction, value creation, and intention to revisit, offering more profound insight into tourist segmentation and personalisation strategies.

b. Comparative Cross-Country Analysis.

Given the global presence of halal tourism, comparative research across different Muslim-majority and Muslim-friendly countries (e.g., Malaysia, Turkey, UAE) could examine whether the mediating role of value creation holds across various cultural and regulatory environments. This would test the generalizability of the model beyond the Indonesian context.

c. Longitudinal Research Design.

Revisit intention is inherently future-oriented. Longitudinal studies can help track whether intentions result in repeat visits and how perceptions of value and attraction evolve.

d. Expansion of the Value Creation Construct.

Further research can deepen our understanding of value creation by examining its multidimensional aspects—for example, emotional, functional, social, and spiritual value—to see which dimensions have the greatest impact in halal tourism settings.

e. Integration with Digital and Smart Tourism.

Future work could explore how digital touchpoints, such as social media engagement, mobile apps, or AI-powered guides, contribute to value creation and influence revisit intention in halal destinations. This aligns with the Service-Dominant Logic (SDL) theory's emphasis on co-creation via technology.

f. Qualitative Studies for Deeper Insight.

While this research appears to be quantitative, qualitative methods such as in-depth interviews or focus groups could uncover nuanced perceptions of value and attraction among Muslim tourists, helping to refine or extend the existing theoretical model.

g. Broader Application of Co-Value Creation and SDL.

Further studies could test the integration of Co-Value Creation Theory and SDL in other niche tourism areas such as eco-halal tourism, medical halal tourism, or luxury halal travel, to see how co-creation dynamics differ across market segments.

References

- 1) Bagozzi, R.P. (1992). The self-regulation of attitudes, intentions, and behaviour. *Soc. Psychol. Q.*, 55, 178–204. [CrossRef]
- 2) Baker, D.A.; Crompton, J.L. Quality, satisfaction and behavioural intentions. *Ann. Tour. Res.* 2000, 27, 785–804. [CrossRef]
- 3) Balaguer, J.; Jordá, M. (2010). Tourism as a long-run economic growth factor: The Spanish case. *Appl. Econ.*, 34, 877–884. [CrossRef]
- 4) Battour, M., Ismail, M. N., & Battor, M. (2011). The impact of destination attributes on Muslim tourist's choice. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 13(6), 527–540, Doi: 10.1002/jtr.824
- 5) Battour, M. K. (2010). *The Impact of Islamic Attributes of Destination on Tourists' Motivation, Satisfaction and Destination Loyalty*, University of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.

- 6) Battour, M. and Ismail, M.N. (2016). "Halal tourism: concepts, practice challenges, and future", *Tourism Management Perspectives*, Vol. 19, pp. 150-154. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2015.12.008>.
- 7) Byon, K.K.; Zhang, J.; Jang, W.(2022E). Examining the Value Co-Creation Model in Motor Racing Events: Moderating Effect of Residents and Tourists. *Sustainability*. 14, 9648. [CrossRef]
- 8) Campos, A. C., Mendes, J., Valle, P. O. D., & Scott, N. (2018). Co-creation of tourist experiences: A literature review. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 21(4), 369-400
- 9) Chen-Ling, & Lie, dalam *Journal of American Academy of Business*.
- 10) Creswell JW. (2014) *Research Design. Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*: Sage publications.
- 11) Dang, L.; Weiss, J. (2010). Evidence on the Relationship between Place Attachment and Behavioral Intentions between 2007 and 2011: A Systematic Literature Review. *Sustainability* 2021, 13, 13138. [CrossRef]
- 12) Direktorat Statistik Keuangan, Teknologi Informasi, dan Pariwisata. 2024. *STATISTIK WISATAWAN NUSANTARA 2023*. Volume 6.
- 13) Grönroos, C. (2008). Service logic revisited: who creates value? And who co-creates? *European Business Review*, 20(4): 298-314. Grönroos, C. (2011). Value co-creation in service logic: A critical analysis. *Marketing Theory*, 11(3): 279–301
- 14) Fyall. (2014) *Pemasaran dalam McCabe, S. (Ed). Buku Pegangan Pemasaran Pariwisata* Routledge. London: Routledge. Hal 151 - 164
- 15) Grönroos, C. (2008). Service logic revisited: who creates value? And who co-creates? *European Business Review*, 20(4): 298-314.
- 16) Grönroos, C. (2011). Value co-creation in service logic: A critical analysis. *Marketing Theory*, 11(3): 279–301.
- 17) Grönroos, C., Voima, P. (2013). Critical service logic: making sense of value creation and cocreation. *Journal of the Academy Marketing Science*, 41(2): 133-150
- 18) Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2014). *Exploratory factor analysis. Multivariate data analysis*, 7th Edition, Pearson new international ed. Harlow: Pearson.
- 19) Junanto. 2020. Perbedaan Persepsi Wisatawan Perempuan dan laki laki. *Mancanegara terhadap Keselamatan dan Keamanan Wisata di Kota Yogyakarta*. Gadjah Mada Journal of Tourism STUDY 2(2).
- 20) Kohler, T.; Fueller, J.; Matzler, K.; Stieger, D.; Füller, J. (2011). Co-Creation in Virtual Worlds: The Design of the User Experience. *MIS Q.*, 35, 773–788. [CrossRef]
- 21) Kotler, Philip, (2000), *Manajemen Pemasaran*, PT. Prenhallindo, Jakarta. Laws, E. *Tourist Destination Management: Issues, Analysis and Policies*; Routledge: Oxfordshire, UK, 1995. Le Blanc, Gaston & Nguyen, Nha. 1996. Cues Used by Customers Evaluating Corporate Image in Service Firms. *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, Vol 7, No. 2, pp. 44-56
- 22) Lindgreen Maciel, J.R.B.R.B., Francisco-Maffezzolli, E.C. and Martins, E. (2018), "*Autenticidade de Lugar: mensuração e influência na seleção de destino de férias*", *Revista Turismo Em Análise*, Vol. 29 No. 3, pp. 413-427, doi: 10.11606/issn.1984-4867.v29i3p413-427.
- 23) Lindgreen A., Antico M., Palmer R. & Tim V.H. (2009). High-tech, innovative products: Identifying and meeting business customers' value needs. *The Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 24(3/4): 182–197

- 24) Lusch R.F., Vargo S.L. (2014). *Service Dominant Logic. Premises, perspectives, possibilities.* Cambridge University Press, New York.
- 25) Lusch, R. F., Vargo, S. L., & O'Brien, M. (2007). Competing through service: Insights from service-dominant logic. *Journal of retailing*, 83(1), 5-18.
- 26) Murray, N., Lynch, P., & Foley, A. (2016). Unlocking the magic in successful tourism destination marketing: The role of sensing capability. *Journal of marketing management*, 32(9-10), 877-899.
- 27) Nugraha, Y. M. (2018). Analisis Potensi Pariwisata Halal di Kepulauan Riau. *Penelitian dan Karya Ilmiah*, 3(2), 63-68
- 28) Payne, A.F., Storbacka, K., & Frow, P. (2008). Managing the co-creation of value. *Journal of Academy Marketing Science*, 36: 83-96.
- 29) Reitsamer, B.F.; Brunner-Sperdin, A.; Stokburger-Sauer, N.E. (2016) Destination attractiveness and destination attachment: The mediating role of tourists' attitude. *Tour. Manag. Perspect.*, 19, 93–101
- 30) Pizam, A.; Tasci, A.D.A. (2019). Experienscape: Expanding the concept of servicescape with a multi-stakeholder and multi-disciplinary approach (invited paper for luminaries' special issue of *International Journal of Hospitality Management*). *Int. J. Hospitality Management*, 76, 25–37. [CrossRef]
- 31) Prahalad, C. K., & Ramaswamy, V. (2001). The collaboration continuum. *Optimize Magazine*, 31-39.
Prahalad, C.K., & Ramaswamy, V. (2004). *The future of competition: Co-Creating unique value with consumer.* Boston: Harvard Business School Press.
- 32) Prebensen, N. & Foss, L. (2011). Coping and Co-creating in Tourist Experiences. *International Journal of Travel Research*, 13: 54–67.
- 33) Prebensen, N. K., & Xie, J. (2017). Efficacy of co-creation and mastering on perceived value and satisfaction in tourists' consumption. *Tourism Management*, 60, 166-176. Prebensen, N.K., Vittersø, J., & Dahl, T. (2013) Value co-creation. Significance of tourist resources. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 42: 240–261.
- 34) Prebensen, N.K., Woo, E., Chen, J. & Uysal, M. (2012). Motivation and involvement as antecedents of the perceived value of the destination experience. *Journal of Travel Research*, (5)2: 253-264.
- 35) Ramaswamy, V. (2005). Co-creating experiences with customers: new paradigm of value creation. *TheTMTTC Journal of Management*, 8, 6-14. Ramadhani.
- 36) Taghizadeh, S. K., Jayaraman, K., Ismail, I., & Rahman, S. A. (2016). Scale development and validation for DART model of value co-creation process on innovation strategy. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 31(1), 24-35
Terapan dan Keuangan (Mankeu) Vol. 12 No.01, Maret P-ISSN: 2252-8636, E-ISSN: 2685-9424 1558
- 37) Salman Yousaf, fan xiucheng (2017) pun (Yusniza Kamarulzaman, Azian binMadun, 2017, Majid et. Al. 2015).2030 (Global travel and tourism industry-Statistics & amp; Facts|Statistika, n.d.).
- 38) Samori, Zakiah, Nor Zafir MD Salleh, dan Mohammad Mahyuddin Khalid. (2016). "Current trends on Halal tourism: Cases on selected Asian countries." *Tourism Management Perspectives* 19: 131–36. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2211973615001014>
- 39) Sekaran U and Bougie R. (2017) *Metode Penelitian untuk Bisnis: Pendekatan Pengembangan-Keahlian: Salemba Empat*
- 40) Taheri, B.; Coelho, F.J.; Sousa, C.M.P.; Evanschitzky, H. Mood regulation, customer participation, and customer value creation in hospitality services. *Int. J. Contemp. Hosp. Manag.* 2017, 29, 3063–3081. [CrossRef]

- 41) Vargo, S.L., & Lusch, R.F. (2004). Evolving to a new dominant logic for marketing. *Journal of Marketing*, 68(1): 1-17.
- 42) Vargo, S.L., & Lusch R.F. (2008a). Service-dominant logic: continuing the evolution. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 36(1): 1-10.
- 43) Vargo, S.L., & Lusch, R.F. (2008b). From goods to service(s): Divergences and convergences of logics. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 37(3): 254-259.
- 44) Vargo, S.L., & Lusch, R.F. (2011). It's all B2B ... and beyond: Toward a systems perspective of the market. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 40: 181-187.
- 45) Vargo, S. L., & Lusch, R. F. (2016). Institutions and axioms: an extension and update of service-dominant logic. *Journal of the Academy of marketing Science*, 44(1), 5-23.
- 46) Vargo, S. L., Maglio, P. P., & Akaka, M. A. (2008). On value and value co-creation: A service systems and service logic perspective. *European management journal*, 26(3), 145-152.
- 47) Voima, P., Heinonen, K., & Strandvik, T. (2010). Exploring customer value formation—a customer dominant logic perspective. Working paper, No. 552, Publications of Hanken School of Economics, Helsinki, Finland.
- 48) Wang, N. (1999). Rethinking authenticity in tourism experience. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 26(2): 349-370.[https://doi.org/10.1016/S01607383\(98\)00103-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S01607383(98)00103-0)
- 49) Wang, Y., & Fesenmaier, D. R. (2007). Collaborative destination marketing: A case study of Elkhart County, Indiana. *Tourism Management*, 28, 863-875.
- 50) Yoeti, O. A. (2008). *Perencanaan Strategis pemasaran daerah tujuan wisata Jakarta: Pradnya Paramita*.
- 51) Yoeti, O. A 1997. *Perencanaan dan Pengembangan Pariwisata*. Jakarata
- 52) Zaenuri, M. (2012). *Perencanaan Strategis Kepariwisataaan Daerah Konsep dan Aplikasi*. In e-Gov Publishing (Vol. 1).
- 53) Zhu Tengting, Zhang Lu, Zeng Chuhong, Liu Xin. (2022). Rethinking value co-creation and loyalty in virtual travel communities: How and when the develop Author links open overlay panel. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services Volume 69*

Websites:

- 1) <https://bincangsyariah.com/https://katadata.co.id/anshar/berita/609a196980894/lima-destinasi-pariwisata-halal-terbaik-indonesihalal>